

On some generalizations of (n, m) -normal powers operators on Hilbert space

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Abstract.

Recall that an operator $T \in B(H)$ is called (n, m) -normal powers operator if and only if $T^n(T^m)^* = (T^m)^*T^n$ for some nonnegative integers n and m . Throughout this paper, we introduce some types of generalizations of (n, m) -normal powers operators and study some of their properties.

Keywords: Normal operators, (n, m) -normal powers operator, n -power quasi-normal operator, n -power class (Q) .

1. Introduction.

Recall that operator $T \in B(H)$ is said to be normal operator if $TT^* = T^*T$. In [3], Alzuraqi introduced a new class of operators n -normal operators which is defined as follows: $T \in B(H)$ is called an n -normal operator if $T^nT^* = T^*T^n$ for some nonnegative integer n . He gave some basic properties of these operators and described the n -normal operators.

In [1], the author suggested the class of (n, m) -normal powers operators and study some properties of such class of operators for different values of the parameters n, m which is defined as follows: $T \in B(H)$ is called (n, m) -normal powers operator if and only if $T^n(T^m)^* = (T^m)^*T^n$ for some nonnegative integers n and m . Clearly, every bounded normal operator is $(1, 1)$ -normal powers operator. Moreover, one can see that every n -normal operator is $(n, 1)$ -normal powers. But the converse is not necessarily true in general. It is simply seen that, $T = \begin{bmatrix} 2 & 1 \\ 0 & -2 \end{bmatrix}$ is $(3, 2)$ -normal powers operator but it is not 3-normal. Hence, the class of n -normal operator is subclass of the class of (n, m) -normal powers operators. For more information about (n, m) -normal powers operators, we can refer the reader to [1] and [2].

In this paper, we establish new classes of operators which are generalizations of (n, m) -normal powers operators on a Hilbert.

2. On (n, m) -Powers Quasi-Normal Operators.

Recall that [4], an operator $T \in B(H)$ is called *quasi-normal* if $T(T^*T) = (T^*T)T$. In [6], the author introduced then-*power quasi-normal* as follows: T is called n -power quasi-normal if and only if $T^n(T^*T) = (T^*T)T^n$ for some nonnegative integer n . It is clear that every quasi-normal operator is 1-power quasi-normal. In this section we introduce a new class of operator, which is called (n, m) -power quasi-normal is introduced as follows:

Definition 2.1: Let $T \in B(H)$, T is called (n, m) -power quasi-normal if and only if $T^n(T^{*m}T) = (T^{*m}T)T^n$ for some nonnegative integers n, m .

It is clear that every quasi-normal operator is $(1, 1)$ -power quasi-normal operator. Moreover, one can see that every n -power quasi-normal operator is $(n, 1)$ -power quasi-normal operator. But the converse is not true in general. It is easily seen that, $T = \begin{bmatrix} 2 & 1 \\ 0 & -2 \end{bmatrix}$ is $(3, 2)$ -power quasi-normal operator but it is not 3-power quasi-normal.

Theorem 2.2: If T is (n, m) -power quasi-normal operator, then so are:

- 1) kT for any scalar k .
- 2) Any $S \in B(H)$ which is unitary equivalent to T .
- 3) The restriction $T|M$ of T to any closed subspace M of H that reduces T .

Proof: Since T is (n, m) -power quasi-normal operator, then $T^n(T^{*m}T) = (T^{*m}T)T^n$ for someative integers n, m .

$$\begin{aligned} 1) (kT)^n ((kT)^{*m} kT) &= k^n T^n (\bar{k}^m T^{*m} kT) = k^n \bar{k}^m k T^n (T^{*m} T) = k^n \bar{k}^m k (T^{*m} T) T^n \\ &= (\bar{k}^m T^{*m} kT) k^n T^n = ((kT)^{*m} kT) (kT)^n. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, kT is (n, m) -power quasi-normal operator.

2) Let $S = UTU^*$, where U is a unitaty operator. Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} S^n (S^{*m} S) &= (U^*TU)^n ((U^*TU)^{*m} (U^*TU)) = U^*T^n U (U^*T^{*m} U U^*TU) = U^*T^n (T^{*m} T) U = U^* (T^{*m} T) T^n U \\ &= (U^*T^{*m} U U^*TU) U^*T^n U = ((U^*TU)^{*m} (U^*TU)) (U^*TU)^n = (S^{*m} S) S^n. \blacksquare \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3) \text{ By [3:p159] we have, } (T|M)^n((T|M)^{m*}(T|M)) &= (T^n|M)((T^{m*}|M)(T|M)) = (T^n(T^{m*}T)|M) = \\ &= ((T^{m*}T)T^n)|M \\ &= ((T^{m*}|M)(T|M))(T^n|M) = ((T|M)^{m*}(T|M))(T|M)^n. \end{aligned}$$

The following theorem proves that the class of (n, m) -normal powers is subclass of (n, m) -power quasi-normal.

Theorem 2.3: If $T \in B(H)$ is a (n, m) -normal powers operator, then T is (n, m) -power quasi-normal.

Proof: Since T is (n, m) -normal powers operator, then $T^n(T^m)^* = (T^m)^*T^n$. Note that,

$$T^n T^{*m} T = T^{*m} T^n T = T^{*m} T^{n+1} = T^{*m} T T^n. \blacksquare$$

Theorem 2.4: Let T and S are (n, m) -power quasi-normal operators, such that T commutes with S and S^* . Then ST is a (n, m) -power quasi-normal operator.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Proof: } (ST)^n((ST)^{*m}(ST)) &= S^n T^n ((S^* T^*)^m (ST)) = (S^n T^n)((S^{*m} T^{*m})(ST)) = S^n T^n S^{*m} ST^{*m} T \\ &= S^n (S^{*m} S) T^n (T^{*m} T) = (S^{*m} S) S^n (T^{*m} T) T^n = S^{*m} S (T^{*m} T) S^n T^n \\ &= (S^{*m} T^{*m} ST) S^n T^n = ((S^* T^*)^m (ST)) S^n T^n = ((ST)^{*m} (ST))(ST)^n. \blacksquare \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 2.5: Let T and S are (n, m) -power quasi-normal operators, such that $ST = TS = T^*S = ST^* = 0$, then $S + T$ is (n, m) -power quasi-normal operator.

Proof:

$$\begin{aligned} (S + T)^n((S + T)^{*m}(S + T)) &= (S^n + T^n)((S^* + T^*)^m(S + T)) = (S^n + T^n)(S^{*m}S + T^{*m}T) \\ &= S^n S^{*m}S + T^n T^{*m}T \\ &= S^{*m}SS^n + T^{*m}TT^n = (S^{*m}S + T^{*m}T)(S^n + T^n) = ((S^* + T^*)^m(S + T))(S^n + T^n) \\ &= ((S + T)^{*m}(S + T))(S + T)^n. \blacksquare \end{aligned}$$

Proposition 2.6: Let T_1, \dots, T_k are (n, m) -power quasi-normal operators. Then $(T_1 \oplus \dots \oplus T_k)$ and $(T_1 \otimes \dots \otimes T_k)$ are (n, m) -power quasi-normal operators.

Proof:

$$\begin{aligned} (T_1 \oplus \dots \oplus T_k)^n((T_1 \oplus \dots \oplus T_k)^{*m}(T_1 \oplus \dots \oplus T_k)) \\ = (T_1^n \oplus \dots \oplus T_k^n)((T_1^{*m} \oplus \dots \oplus T_k^{*m})(T_1 \oplus \dots \oplus T_k)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= T_1^n (T_1^{*m} T_1) \oplus \cdots \oplus T_k^n (T_k^{*m} T_k) \\
 &= (T_1^{*m} T_1) T_1^n \oplus \cdots \oplus (T_k^{*m} T_k) T_k^n \\
 &= ((T_1^{*m} \oplus \cdots \oplus T_k^{*m})(T_1 \oplus \cdots \oplus T_k))(T_1^n \oplus \cdots \oplus T_k^n) \\
 &= ((T_1 \oplus \cdots \oplus T_k)^{*m} (T_1 \oplus \cdots \oplus T_k))(T_1 \oplus \cdots \oplus T_k)^n.
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $(T_1 \oplus \cdots \oplus T_k)$ is a (n, m) -power quasi-normal operator. Now, let $x_1, \dots, x_k \in H$, then

$$\begin{aligned}
 &(T_1 \otimes \cdots \otimes T_k)^n ((T_1 \otimes \cdots \otimes T_k)^{*m} (T_1 \otimes \cdots \otimes T_k))(x_1 \otimes \cdots \otimes x_k) \\
 &= (T_1^n \otimes \cdots \otimes T_k^n) ((T_1^{*m} \otimes \cdots \otimes T_k^{*m})(T_1 \otimes \cdots \otimes T_k))(x_1 \otimes \cdots \otimes x_k) \\
 &= (T_1^n (T_1^{*m} T_1) \otimes \cdots \otimes T_k^n (T_k^{*m} T_k))(x_1 \otimes \cdots \otimes x_k) \\
 &= ((T_1^{*m} T_1) T_1^n \otimes \cdots \otimes (T_k^{*m} T_k) T_k^n)(x_1 \otimes \cdots \otimes x_k) \\
 &= ((T_1^{*m} \otimes \cdots \otimes T_k^{*m})(T_1 \otimes \cdots \otimes T_k))(T_1^n \otimes \cdots \otimes T_k^n)(x_1 \otimes \cdots \otimes x_k) \\
 &= ((T_1 \otimes \cdots \otimes T_k)^{*m} (T_1 \otimes \cdots \otimes T_k))(T_1 \otimes \cdots \otimes T_k)^n (x_1 \otimes \cdots \otimes x_k).
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $(T_1 \otimes \cdots \otimes T_k)$ is a (n, m) -power quasi-normal.

3. On (n, m) -Power Class (Q) Operators.

Recall that [5], an operator $T \in B(H)$ is called *class*(Q) operator if $T^{*2}T^2 = (T^*T)^2$. In [7] the authors introduced the n -power *class*(Q) operator as follows: $T \in B(H)$ is called n -power class (Q) operator if and only if $T^{*2}T^{2n} = (T^*T^n)^2$ for some nonnegative integer n . It is clear that every class (Q) operator is 1-power class. In this section we introduce a new class of operator, which is called (n, m) -power class (Q) is introduced as follows:

Definition 3.1: Let $T \in B(H)$, T is called (n, m) -power *class*(Q) operator if and only if $T^{*2m}T^{2n} = (T^{m*}T^n)^2$ for some nonnegative integers n, m .

It is clear that, every class (Q) operator is $(1,1)$ -power class (Q) operator. Moreover, one can see that every n -power class (Q) operator is $(n, 1)$ -power class (Q) operator. But the converse is not true in general. It is easily seen that, $T = \begin{bmatrix} 2 & 1 \\ 0 & -2 \end{bmatrix}$ is (n, m) -powers class (Q) operator but it is not class (Q) and not 3-power class (Q).

Theorem 3.2: If T is (n, m) -power class (Q) operator, then so are:

- 1) kT for every scalar k .

2) Any $S \in B(H)$ that is unitary equivalent to T .

3) The restriction $T|M$ of T to any closed subspace M of H that reduces T .

Proof : Since T is (n, m) -power class (Q) operator, then $T^{*2m}T^{2n} = (T^mT^n)^2$

$$\begin{aligned} 1) \quad (kT)^{*2m}(kT)^{2n} &= \bar{k}^{2m}T^{*2m}k^{2n}T^{2n} = \bar{k}^{2m}k^{2n}T^{*2m}T^{2n} = (\bar{k}^m k^n)^2 (T^m T^n)^2 \\ &= (\bar{k}^m k^n T^m T^n)^2 = (\bar{k}^m T^m k^n T^n)^2 = ((kT)^{*m}(kT)^n)^2. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, kT is (n, m) -power class (Q) operator.

2) Let $S = UTU^*$, where U is a unitary operator. Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} S^{*2m}S^{2n} &= (U^*TU)^{*2m}(U^*TU)^{2n} = U^*T^{*2m}UU^*T^{2n}U = U^*T^{*2m}T^{2n}U = U^*(T^mT^n)^2U \\ &= U^*(T^mT^n)UU^*(T^mT^n)U = (U^*T^mT^nU)^2 = (U^*T^mUU^*T^nU)^2 = (S^*mS^n)^2. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, S is (n, m) -powers class (Q) operator.

3) By [3:p159] we have,

$$(T|M)^{*2m}(T|M)^{2n} = (T^{*2m}|M)(T^{2n}|M) = (T^{*2m}T^{2n}|M) = (T^mT^n)^2|M = ((T|M)^{*m}(T|M)^n)^2. \blacksquare$$

Theorem 3.3: If $T \in B(H)$ is (n, m) -normal powers operator, then T is (n, m) -power class (Q) .

Proof : Since T is (n, m) -normal powers operator, then $T^n(T^m)^* = (T^m)^*T^n$. Note that,

$$T^{*2m}T^{2n} = T^*mT^*mT^nT^n = T^*mT^nT^*mT^n = (T^*mT^n)^2. \blacksquare$$

The above theorem proves that the class of all (n, m) -normal powers operator is subclass of the class of (n, m) -power class (Q) . In addition that, the next theorem proves that the class of all (n, m) -powers quasi-normal operator is subclass of the class of (n, m) -power class (Q) .

Theorem 3.4: If $T \in B(H)$ is (n, m) -powers quasi-normal operator, then T is (n, m) -power class (Q) .

Proof:

Since T is (n, m) -powers quasi-normal operator, then $T^n(T^m)^*T = (T^m)^*T^n$. Note that,

$$T^{*2m}T^{2n} = T^*mT^*mT^nT^n = T^*mT^*mT^nT^{n-1} = T^*mT^nT^*mT^nT^{n-1} = T^*mT^nT^*mT^n = (T^*mT^n)^2. \blacksquare$$

Proposition 3.5: Let T_1, \dots, T_k are (n, m) -power class (Q) operators. Then $(T_1 \oplus \dots \oplus T_k)$ and $(T_1 \otimes \dots \otimes T_k)$ are (n, m) -power class (Q) operators.

Proof :

$$\begin{aligned}
 (T_1 \oplus \dots \oplus T_k)^{*2m} (T_1 \oplus \dots \oplus T_k)^{2n} &= (T_1^{*2m} \oplus \dots \oplus T_k^{*2m})(T_1^{2n} \oplus \dots \oplus T_k^{2n}) \\
 &= T_1^{*2m} T_1^{2n} \oplus \dots \oplus T_k^{*2m} T_k^{2n} \\
 &= (T_1^{*m} T_1^n)^2 \oplus \dots \oplus (T_k^{*m} T_k^n)^2 = (T_1^{*m} T_1^n)(T_1^{*m} T_1^n) \oplus \dots \oplus (T_k^{*m} T_k^n)(T_k^{*m} T_k^n) \\
 &= (T_1^{*m} T_1^n \oplus \dots \oplus T_k^{*m} T_k^n)^2 = ((T_1^{*m} \oplus \dots \oplus T_k^{*m})(T_1^n \oplus \dots \oplus T_k^n))^2 \\
 &= ((T_1 \oplus \dots \oplus T_k)^{*m} (T_1 \oplus \dots \oplus T_k)^n)^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $(T_1 \oplus \dots \oplus T_k)$ is a (n, m) -power class (Q) operator. Now, let $x_1, \dots, x_k \in H$, then

$$\begin{aligned}
 (T_1 \otimes \dots \otimes T_k)^{*2m} (T_1 \otimes \dots \otimes T_k)^{2n} (x_1 \otimes \dots \otimes x_k) &= (T_1^{*2m} \otimes \dots \otimes T_k^{*2m})(T_1^{2n} \otimes \dots \otimes T_k^{2n})(x_1 \otimes \dots \otimes x_k) \\
 &= (T_1^{*2m} T_1^{2n} \otimes \dots \otimes T_k^{*2m} T_k^{2n})(x_1 \otimes \dots \otimes x_k) = T_1^{*2m} T_1^{2n} x_1 \otimes \dots \otimes T_k^{*2m} T_k^{2n} x_k \\
 &= (T_1^{*m} T_1^n x_1)^2 \otimes \dots \otimes (T_k^{*m} T_k^n x_k)^2 = (T_1^{*m} T_1^n x_1 \otimes \dots \otimes T_k^{*m} T_k^n x_k)^2 \\
 &= ((T_1^{*m} \otimes \dots \otimes T_k^{*m})(T_1^n \otimes \dots \otimes T_k^n)(x_1 \otimes \dots \otimes x_k))^2 \\
 &= ((T_1 \otimes \dots \otimes T_k)^{*m} (T_1 \otimes \dots \otimes T_k)^n (x_1 \otimes \dots \otimes x_k))^2 \\
 &= ((T_1 \otimes \dots \otimes T_k)^{*m} (T_1 \otimes \dots \otimes T_k)^n)^2 (x_1 \otimes \dots \otimes x_k).
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $(T_1 \otimes \dots \otimes T_k)$ is a (n, m) -power class (Q) operator. ■

Proposition 3.6: Let $T \in B(H)$. Then T is a (n, m) -power class (Q) operator if and only if T is a (m, n) -power class (Q) operator.

Proof : Let, T is (n, m) -power class (Q) operator, then $T^{*2m} T^{2n} = (T^{*m} T^n)^2$. Note that,

$$T^{*2n} T^{2m} = (T^{*2m} T^{2n})^* = ((T^{*m} T^n)^2)^* = ((T^{*m} T^n)^*)^2 = (T^{*n} T^m)^2.$$

Thus, T is a (m, n) -power class (Q) . The converse of the proposition is similar. ■

Theorem 3.7: Let T and S are (n, m) -power class (Q) operators, such that T commutes with S and S^* . Then ST is a (n, m) -power class (Q) operator.

Proof :

$$\begin{aligned}
 (ST)^{*2m} (ST)^{2n} &= T^{*2m} S^{*2m} S^{2n} T^{2n} = T^{*2m} T^{2n} S^{*2m} S^{2n} = T^{*2m} T^{2n} (S^{*m} S^n)^2 = (T^{*m} T^n)^2 (S^{*m} S^n)^2 \\
 &= (T^{*m} T^n S^{*m} S^n)^2 = (T^{*m} S^{*m} T^n S^n)^2 = ((S^m T^m)^* S^n T^n)^2 = ((ST)^{*m} (ST)^n)^2. \quad \blacksquare
 \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 3.8: The class of all (n, m) -power class (Q) operators on H is closed subset of $B(H)$ under scalar multiplication.

Proof : Put, $Q(H) = \{T \in B(H): T \text{ is a } (n, m)\text{-powers class } (Q) \text{ operator on } H \text{ for some nonnegative integer } n, m\}$.

One can show that from theorem (5.1), $\alpha T \in Q(H)$ for any scalar α , therefore the scalar multiplication is closed under $Q(H)$. Now let T_k be a sequence in $B(H)$ of (n, m) -power class (Q) converges to T , then after simple computation one can see that, $\|T^{2m*}T^{2n} - (T^{m*}T^n)^2\| = \|T^{2m*}T^{2n} - T_k^{2m*}T_k^{2n} + (T_k^{m*}T_k^n)^2 - (T^{m*}T^n)^2\|$

$$\leq \|T^{2m*}T^{2n} - T_k^{2m*}T_k^{2n}\| + \|(T_k^{m*}T_k^n)^2 - (T^{m*}T^n)^2\| \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } k \rightarrow \infty.$$

This implies that, $T^{2m*}T^{2n} = (T^{m*}T^n)^2$, therefore $T \in Q(H)$. Hence, $Q(H)$ is closed under scalar multiplication.

From the previous we get the following inclusions of classes:

Normal \subsetneq (n, m) -normal powers \subsetneq (n, m) -powers quasi-normal \subsetneq (n, m) -power class (Q) .

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